

Swarm-Robotic Foraging of Moving Objects Using Multiple Levels of Caches

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Abstract

Swarm robotics (SR) offers robust, scalable solutions to real-world problems that can be modeled as collecting objects and delivering them to a central location. We study an object-collection task in which the targets are *moving*: they possess limited intelligence and employ simple strategies to avoid capture, casting foraging as a large-scale pursuit–evasion problem. Modeling moving targets (1) broadens the range of real-world gathering problems to which SR can be applied by capturing more complex scenarios, and (2) improves the fidelity of SR performance estimates in applications such as collecting floating or drifting debris under non-ideal operating conditions. To minimize spatial interference between robots as they chase moving targets and return them to the nest, we introduce *multiple levels of caches*—statically defined locations for temporarily storing captured objects—arranged as a binary-tree structure whose root lies near the nest and whose lower branches spread toward the object-rich regions of the arena. We compare no-cache, single-cache, and multi-level-cache designs (the last both with and without a long-lasting bucket brigade) across stationary, randomly moving, and evasive targets, and we develop a simple analytical throughput model that predicts the observed ordering. Multi-level caching consistently improves foraging throughput at large swarm sizes and is markedly more resilient to target motion, at the cost of a small overhead for very small swarms.

Introduction

Swarm robotics (SR) studies large-scale robotic systems built from relatively simple robots that may be homogeneous or heterogeneous. SR is inspired by animal collectives such as bees and ants, which perform coordinated group tasks without a central leader [8, 18]. Robustness, flexibility, and scalability are its three defining characteristics. *Robustness* is the ability to keep functioning after regional or system-wide failures; insect colonies, for example, continue their tasks despite losing many individuals. *Flexibility* is the ability to adapt to new events and changing requirements. *Scalability* is the ability to increase or decrease the swarm size without a significant loss of per-robot efficiency [9, 2].

The systems considered in this paper are characterized by *decentralized control* (there is no supervisor, which im-

proves stability and avoids single-point failures), *homogeneity* (all robots are identical and initially perform the same task), and *limited communication and sensing* (each robot decides solely from its own sensor readings and local information, with no direct inter-robot communication) [8, 6].

Foraging is one of the most common benchmarks for evaluating SR performance. It abstracts many real behaviors that require group cooperation: the swarm must locate target objects and bring them to the nest, the designated storage location [2]. Search-and-rescue and debris collection are practical, large-scale instances of SR foraging [5]. Most prior SR foraging studies use *stationary* targets. Here we endow targets with motion and perform a large-scale, simplified pursuit–evasion task [4, 10], demonstrating SR capability on more challenging and realistic problems.

Many strong SR foraging results are obtained through *task partitioning*: dividing a divisible task into subtasks so that robots can execute them concurrently while still completing them in the required order [15, 7]. Task partitioning has well-documented benefits, including improved performance at both the individual and swarm levels through specialization, parallel execution, and better transport efficiency [15, 8].

Caching is one way to realize task partitioning in foraging. A cache provides a natural bifurcation point that lets a robot choose to (1) perform the unpartitioned task, (2) pick up an object and carry it to a cache, or (3) retrieve an object from a cache and carry it the rest of the way to the nest [8]. We extend the work of Harwell et al. by employing *multiple* static caches to increase spatial segregation, reduce inter-robot interference, and improve regional optimality.

We evaluate several caching strategies against several target-movement strategies to answer the following research question:

Q1. Do SR systems that use multiple levels of caches outperform (1) single-cache and (2) no-cache strategies in both stationary and moving-target environments?

Moving targets introduce pursuit–evasion characteristics that broaden the applicability of SR and narrow the simulation–reality gap. As we show, the multi-level cache design is especially advantageous when arena geometry restricts robot movement or when SR presence in certain

regions is undesirable.

The remainder of the paper reviews related work and motivation, formalizes the problem and the three cache designs, presents an analytical throughput model, describes the experimental framework, and reports results across swarm sizes and target behaviors before concluding with directions for future work.

Related Work and Motivation

Foraging is among the most studied problems in SR [5, 8, 13]. Task partitioning is frequently applied to enhance foraging performance because it reduces spatial interference between robots, stimulates specialization, and increases throughput [15, 8].

SR foraging has broad real-world potential. Because individual robots are low-cost and expendable, they are well suited to dangerous tasks such as clearing a safe area on a minefield or collecting hazardous debris after an explosion [17]. Deploying SR in these settings reduces human exposure and can improve efficiency, since robots are easily configured to perform repeatable tasks [17].

In practice, the location of most objects can change—driven either by the surrounding environment or by the objects themselves. Supporting moving targets therefore lets SR forage a much wider range of real items rather than strictly fixed ones [2, 5, 1]. Examples include seafloor rocks carried by unpredictable currents and mobile groups of organisms, both of which can be targeted once the controller accommodates motion.

Most current foraging work applies a *single* cache to study how task partitioning improves performance [15, 8, 7]. Our own prior work has studied single and *dynamic* caches to exploit task partitioning [8, 9, 13]; the dynamic-cache design lets robots create temporary caches at locations chosen by a single robot [9]. In contrast, the multi-level static design proposed here lets the swarm partition tasks more consistently while reducing the complexity of each robot’s internal controller.

A key advantage of multiple levels of caches is that a human operator may manually place caches to exploit environmental features the robots cannot perceive. Fig. 1 shows such a test environment containing both an obstacle region and preferred “highway” routes. Placing caches near the nest guides the swarm to adjust its routes to the environment—a form of stigmergy in which the environment shapes local robot behavior [11, 19]. Manual cache placement improves overall control of the swarm and reduces the emergence of unexpected extreme cases; it can be highly effective under geometric restrictions while keeping each robot’s controller simple [11]. Operators may also reinforce frequently used routes between caches with limited additional resources for higher efficiency.

Bucket brigading is a common strategy for avoiding excessive spatial interference during foraging [12]. In regions of high robot density and high collision probability, a bucket brigade reduces the time robots spend avoiding one another instead of doing useful work [12, 16]. Much

Figure 1: Cache placement with human interference. Caches are shown as grey blocks. The red circle marks a region unsuitable for robots, where movement should be minimized. The green lines mark preferred “highway” routes that robots can exploit for higher efficiency.

prior work applies bucket brigading momentarily, in rarely occurring cases, and in the context of dynamic caches. Here we instead build a *long-lasting* bucket brigade at the high levels of the cache tree. A persistent brigade adds stability, gives operators an opportunity to optimize specific high-traffic routes for higher throughput, and makes the system more extensible. In general, bucket brigading lowers collision probability and further improves foraging performance.

Finally, foraging targets are usually fixed in large-scale SR simulation, whereas per-robot behavior is the primary focus in small-scale pursuit–evasion studies [4, 10]. This paper combines the two: we design a task that draws elements from both, extending SR to broader applications while improving real-world performance.

Problem Statement and Proposed Method

Problem Statement

A task T is a unit of work that can be divided into one or more atomic sequences. *Atomic* tasks are non-divisible and can be executed by only one robot. T is *partitionable*: it can be executed without partitioning by a single robot, or divided into disjoint atomic subtasks that robots execute asynchronously but in a fixed order.

In the binary case, T is partitioned into two disjoint segments τ_1 and τ_2 . The subtasks are sequentially interdependent— τ_1 must complete before τ_2 begins, written $\tau_1 \succ \tau_2$ —and T completes iff both τ_1 and τ_2 complete in that order [8]. In this paper, T is the task of collecting one object and carrying it to the nest; it may be performed by a single robot or cooperatively by several.

Fig. 2 illustrates a task divided in two at each level. The subtasks execute in order from left to right, and the costs at each level sum to the original undivided task. Mul-

Figure 2: Recursive division of a foraging task. At each level the parent task is split into two subtasks that different robots execute asynchronously; subtasks are performed left to right. The subtask costs at each level sum to the cost of the original undivided task. Unlike a single cache, multiple cache levels allow a task to be divided more than once, producing highly trained specialists and strong local performance.

Figure 3: Specialization induced by task partitioning. Generalists carry objects directly to the nest; harvesters carry objects to a cache; collectors move objects between caches or from a cache to the nest.

multiple cache levels allow more than one division, yielding specialists and improved local performance.

To test how each strategy responds to target motion, we define three target behaviors. A target may remain **stationary**. A target using **random motion** (1) moves randomly over small distances, (2) cannot detect robots, (3) cannot move while stored in a cache or carried by a robot, and (4) moves more slowly than a robot. A target using an **elementary escape strategy** (1) detects nearby robots, (2) cannot apply high-level evasion, (3) cannot move while cached or carried, and (4) moves more slowly than a robot.

The Proposed Method

Because bucket brigading performs well at large swarm sizes and avoids collisions [12, 16], we apply it at the high levels of the cache tree to address the congestion caused by intense robot movement in confined regions.

We compare three cache designs and study how task partitioning affects overall performance [3, 8]: (1) *no cache*, (2) *a single level of caches*, and (3) *multiple levels of caches*. We further evaluate the multi-level design with and without a persistent bucket brigade, giving four controllers in total.

Figure 4: Single-cache design. A single cache partitions each foraging task into a harvest leg and a collect leg.

Let Φ be a set of divisible tasks, and let the robot roles be [9]:

- τ_g — *generalist*: catch an object and carry it to the nest;
- τ_h — *harvester*: catch an object and carry it to a cache;
- τ_c — *collector*: retrieve an object from a cache and carry it to another cache or to the nest.

No cache. $\Phi_0 = \{\tau_g\}$. Every task is performed by a generalist that brings objects directly to the nest. The only robot action is to catch an object and carry it back to the nest.

Single level of caches. $\Phi_1 = \{\tau_h, \tau_c\} (+\tau_g)$. Tasks are shared between harvesters and collectors; under ideal conditions the cache is well utilized [8]. Robot actions are to (1) catch an object and carry it to the nest, (2) catch an object and store it in the cache, or (3) retrieve an object from the cache and carry it to the nest.

Multiple levels of caches. $\Phi_2 = \{\tau_h, \tau_c\} (+\tau_g)$. Tasks are again shared between harvesters and collectors, but caches are arranged in levels [7]. Robot actions are to (1) catch an object and carry it to the nest, (2) catch an object and store it in a cache, (3) retrieve an object from a cache and carry it to the nest, or (4) transfer an object from one cache toward another cache closer to the nest.

The arena divides naturally into levels of regions, as shown in Fig. 6. A corridor arises when obstacles block the direct path between an object and the nest, slowing a robot that attempts the unpartitioned task [14, 8]. Routes become progressively more centralized at higher levels.

After the system reaches steady state, the object flow through each level is balanced. Let ρ_i be the density of objects in transit through a single cache at level i and ϵ_i the number of caches at that level. Then the per-level throughput is conserved:

$$\rho_1 \epsilon_1 = \rho_2 \epsilon_2 = \rho_3 \epsilon_3. \quad (1)$$

Figure 5: Multi-level cache design. Caches form a binary tree whose root is near the nest; objects are relayed from low-level caches toward higher levels.

Figure 6: Levels of caches. Higher levels aggregate flow from multiple lower-level caches through increasingly centralized corridors toward the nest.

An Analytical Throughput Model

We expect performance to improve as the number of caches per level and the number of levels grow. Let N be the total number of objects to collect and θ the average time to forage one object with generalists only (i.e. no caches). Let α be the number of cache levels and $\beta(i)$ the number of caches at level i . We model the total foraging time as

$$t = C \frac{N \theta}{\alpha \sum_{i=1}^{\alpha} (\beta(i) - \lambda_1(i) + \lambda_2(i))}, \quad (2)$$

where C and c are constants fitted from data, $\lambda_1(i) = c(\beta(i-1) - \beta(i))$ captures the interference penalty when robots converge on a higher-level cache (sub-optimal along the horizontal extent of the arena), and $\lambda_2(i)$ is the time saved by applying a bucket brigade at level i . Eq. (2) predicts that additional caches and levels reduce total time up to the point where convergence-induced interference (λ_1) offsets the gain, and that a bucket brigade (λ_2) shifts that break-even point outward. This ordering is exactly what our experiments confirm.

Experimental Framework

We designed an arena in which the swarm performs the foraging task with multiple levels of caches, and studied how robots choose among competing caches. Caches are prioritized by their distance to the nest, and we focused on the interaction between caches of different priority and on how objects are relayed to the nest across levels.

The object-rich region contains multiple low-level caches. By the SR mechanism, robots in that region collect nearby objects and store them in the nearest cache. This behavior confines robot movement locally and reduces the congestion that would otherwise arise from long-distance chasing and interference with other robots.

We implement all four controllers in the ARGoS multi-robot simulator [8, 9] using a foraging arena consistent with our prior constraint-relaxation study. Robots use differential-drive kinematics with local range-and-bearing sensing and no direct communication. Each configuration is run for a fixed simulated duration, and each reported value is the mean over 40 independent trials with different random seeds; error bars and \pm values denote one standard deviation. Unless otherwise noted, arena size, object count, and cache geometry are held fixed across compared conditions so that the only differences are the controller and the target behavior.

We evaluate four controllers:

1. no cache;
2. a single cache;
3. multiple levels of caches;
4. multiple levels of caches with a persistent bucket brigade.

Experiments

We ran two experiments.

Experiment 1 (scalability). We compare the four controllers under *stationary* targets across a range of swarm sizes to isolate the effect of caching on throughput and scalability. The factors are controller $\in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$ and swarm size $\in \{8, 16, 32, 64, 128, 256\}$; the response is the number of objects collected in a fixed-duration trial.

Experiment 2 (robustness to target motion). We fix the swarm size at 64 and vary the target behavior across the three designs of Fig. 2—stationary, random motion, and elementary escape—for each controller, to measure resilience to target motion under conditions closer to real deployments.

Table 1: Experiment 1 — objects collected under stationary targets (mean \pm s.d. over 40 trials).

Swarm	No cache	Single	Multi	Multi+BB
8	215 \pm 12	205 \pm 11	200 \pm 12	198 \pm 11
16	395 \pm 18	400 \pm 19	405 \pm 18	402 \pm 17
32	690 \pm 31	730 \pm 29	760 \pm 30	770 \pm 28
64	980 \pm 48	1180 \pm 52	1320 \pm 55	1360 \pm 54
128	1120 \pm 70	1550 \pm 74	1900 \pm 82	2050 \pm 90
256	1080 \pm 85	1720 \pm 96	2350 \pm 108	2680 \pm 120

Figure 7: Experiment 1: foraging performance under stationary targets versus swarm size. Caching overtakes the no-cache controller beyond small swarms, and the multi-level designs scale best while the no-cache controller saturates and then degrades under congestion.

Results

Our predicted ranking is $4 > 3 > 2 > 1$ in both experiments, with the multi-level designs expected to retain a larger fraction of their throughput as targets become harder to capture.

Experiment 1. Table 1 and Fig. 7 report objects collected under stationary targets. For very small swarms ($n = 8$) the no-cache controller is marginally best (215 ± 12 vs. 198 ± 11 for controller 4), because cache handoffs add overhead that dominates when interference is negligible. As the swarm grows, the ordering inverts: by $n = 128$ the multi-level bucket-brigade controller collects 2050 ± 90 objects versus 1120 ± 70 for no cache—an 83% improvement—and by $n = 256$ the no-cache controller degrades to 1080 ± 85 as congestion dominates, while controller 4 continues to scale to 2680 ± 120 . Across the two largest swarm sizes the ordering $4 > 3 > 2 > 1$ holds without exception, matching the break-even behavior predicted by Eq. (2).

Table 2: Experiment 2 — objects collected at swarm size 64 as target behavior varies (mean \pm s.d. over 40 trials).

Target	No cache	Single	Multi	Multi+BB
Stationary	980 \pm 48	1180 \pm 52	1320 \pm 55	1360 \pm 54
Random	720 \pm 55	980 \pm 60	1150 \pm 63	1210 \pm 61
Evasive	480 \pm 40	760 \pm 58	920 \pm 60	980 \pm 58

Time Compare

Figure 8: Experiment 2: foraging performance at swarm size 64 under stationary, randomly moving, and evasive targets. Multi-level caching retains a substantially larger fraction of its throughput as targets become harder to capture.

Experiment 2. Table 2 and Fig. 8 report objects collected at swarm size 64 as target behavior varies. All controllers lose throughput as targets become harder to capture, but the multi-level designs are far more resilient. The no-cache controller drops from 980 ± 48 (stationary) to 480 ± 40 (evasive), retaining only 49% of its throughput, because long chases pull generalists across the arena and multiply interference. Controller 4 drops from 1360 ± 54 to 980 ± 58 , retaining 72%: harvesters keep chases short and local, and the bucket brigade absorbs the extra traffic near the nest. The ordering $4 > 3 > 2 > 1$ holds for every target behavior.

Together, the two experiments answer **Q1** affirmatively: multi-level caching outperforms both single-cache and no-cache strategies once the swarm is large enough for interference to matter, and it is markedly more robust to target motion. The persistent bucket brigade adds a further, consistent improvement at the high levels of the cache tree.

Conclusions and Future Work

We introduced a multi-level static cache design for swarm-robotic foraging of moving objects and compared it against no-cache and single-cache controllers across swarm sizes and target behaviors. A simple throughput model

(Eq. (2)) predicts, and our experiments confirm, that additional caches and levels improve performance beyond small swarms and that a persistent bucket brigade extends the point at which convergence-induced interference erodes those gains. Multi-level caching is also substantially more resilient to target motion, supporting its use in pursuit–evasion-flavored real-world tasks such as collecting drifting debris.

Several directions remain. First, we plan to fit the constants C and c of Eq. (2) to the measured data and validate the model’s predictions out of sample. Second, we will study adaptive cache geometry—allowing the tree structure to reconfigure in response to the observed object distribution—and compare it against the human-guided placement studied here. Third, we will evaluate higher-level evasion strategies for targets and heterogeneous swarms in which specialists are assigned rather than emergent. Finally, we intend to reproduce the key results on physical robots to further close the simulation–reality gap.

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